

Isocoumarins: Part III—Synthesis of 3,4-Dimethylisocoumarins

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Synthesis of 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins by effecting cyclodehydration of α -methylacetyl esters of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid and of its derivatives has been developed. Action of aq. NaOH on these isocoumarins has led to the synthesis of ($\pm$) α -methyl- α -(2-carboxyphenyl) acetone derivatives which cyclodehydrate readily to give the original isocoumarins. Oxidation of these acetone derivatives with sodium hypobromite has furnished the corresponding ($\pm$) α -methyl-homophthalic acids. Action of ammonia on these isocoumarins furnished the corresponding isoquinolone derivatives.

3, 4-Dimethylisocoumarins have gained importance owing to the isolation of Oospa-lactone¹ (8-hydroxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarin), a naturally occurring isocoumarin from microorganism *Oospara*. Its synthesis from 7-methoxy-3-methylndarone is reported recently². In the present work, synthesis of few 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins has been achieved by a simple method, adopting a procedure similar to the one developed earlier for the synthesis of 4-methylisocoumarins³.

α -Methylacetyl esters of 3-methoxy- and 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acids (Ia and Ib; X=OMe) were prepared in excellent yields by condensing these acids with 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone in presence of potassium carbonate. The ester (Ia, X=OMe) cyclodehydrated readily in presence of 90% sulphuric acid to furnish a mixture of isomeric 7-methoxy- and 5-methoxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarins (IIa, X=OMe and IIc; Y=OMe), the condensation having taken place in the positions '6' and '2' respectively of the phenyl ring of the ester. The 7-methoxy isomer (IIa, X=OMe) was obtained as major product, whilst the 5-methoxy isomer (IIc, Y=OMe) was obtained as minor product in negligible amounts. This can be expected as the position 2 in the phenyl ring of the ester (Ia, X=OMe) is sterically hindered by the bulky methoxy group in the position 3. The ester (Ib, X=OMe) on cyclodehydration in presence of sulphuric acid furnished 7-methoxy-3, 4, 6-trimethylisocoumarin (IIb, X=OMe) as the major product in excellent yield. The other isomer (IId, Y=OMe) could not be isolated in pure condition, though it appeared to have been formed in a very small quantity. The u.v. absorption curves and $\lambda_{\max}$ of these isocoumarins agreed well with those of the other isocoumarins,^{3,4} thus confirming the isocoumarin ring in their structures.

I

II

1. I. Yamamoto, *Agri. Biol. Chem.*, (Tokyo) 1961, **25**, 400; *C. A.* 1961, **55**, 23670.
2. M. Matsui, K. Moni and Y. Ozawa, *Agri. Biol. Chem.*, 1966, **30** (2), 193; *C. A.*, 1966, **62** 17526.
3. H. K. Dasai and R. N. Usgaonkar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 821.
4. (a) R. D. Haworth, H. K. Pindred and P. R. Jefferies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3617.
(b) J. E. Hay and L. J. Haynes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2231.

III

IV

V

a, R=H, Y=H

b, R=Me, Y=H

c, R=H, X=H

d, R=Me, X=H

Action of aq. NaOH on these 3, 4-dimethylisocoumarins (II) led to the opening of the lactonic ring to furnish the corresponding ($\pm$) α -methyl- α -(2-carboxyphenyl) acetone derivatives (III) after acidification. These ketones (III) readily cyclodehydrated in presence of sulphuric acid to give the original isocoumarins (II).

The constitution of 7-methoxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIa, X=OMe) was established by degradative oxidation of the ketone IIIa (X = OMe) [obtained by hydrolysis of IIa (X = OMe)] when 4-methoxyphthalic acid and a crude oily substance was obtained. The latter on further oxidation with alkaline sodium hypobromite furnished 4-methoxyphthalic acid suggesting that the oily substance was mostly 2-carboxy-4-methoxyacetophenone. A third nonacidic and steam volatile product was also isolated but in negligible amounts and could not be investigated further. The constitution of the other isomer as 5-methoxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIc, Y=OMe) naturally followed. The constitution of the isocoumarin (IIb, X=OMe) has been assigned by analogy with that of IIa (X=OMe) as it happened to be the major product in the cyclodehydration of the ester Ib (X=OMe), the condensation having been assumed to have taken place in the unhindered position '6' in the ester Ib (X = OMe).

The methoxyisocoumarins (IIa, IIb; X=OMe and IIc; Y = OMe) have been successfully demethylated with hydriodic acid and acetic anhydride to furnish the corresponding hydroxyisocoumarins (IIa, IIb; X=OH and IIc; Y = OH). Fries migration of acetoxy derivatives of these isocoumarins was not successful and so also Friedel-Crafts acetylation of the hydroxyisocoumarins. The methoxyisocoumarins (II) on treating with ammonia furnished the corresponding isoquinolones (V).

Cyclodehydration of α -methylacetyl 3-hydroxybenzoate (Ia, X=OH) furnished a mixture of 7-hydroxy- and 5-hydroxy-3, 4-dimethylisocoumarins (IIa, X = OH and IIc, Y = OH) in nearly equal amounts. The 7-hydroxy isomer was isolated in pure state by fractional crystallisation but the other isomer could not be obtained in pure state.

Oxidation of the acetone derivatives IIIa and IIIb ($X = \text{OMe}$) with sodium hypobromite furnished ($\pm$) α -methyl-homophthalic acids IVa and IVb ($X = \text{OMe}$) respectively in good yields, thus providing a method of practical significance for their synthesis. These ($\pm$) α -methylhomophthalic acids would be excellent intermediates for the synthesis of the other isocoumarin derivatives.

The cyclodehydration reaction of the α -methyl acetyl esters (I) is accompanied with the competing reaction of hydrolysis of the esters to give the original acids but it is to be noted that in comparison to the acetyl esters reported earlier³ the hydrolysis of the α -methylacetyl esters takes place to a much smaller extent. Anhydrous aluminium chloride as cyclodehydrating agent was not successful. The ester (I) got hydrolysed readily to give the acid in presence of it.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Methylacetyl 3-methoxybenzoate (Ia, $X = \text{OMe}$): A mixture of 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone⁵ (3 g), *m*-methoxybenzoic acid (3 g), potassium carbonate (1.6 g), methanol (30 ml.) and water (3 ml.) was refluxed for 17 hr., cooled and then filtered to remove KBr. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in ether, washed well with water and then ether was recovered. The oily liquid distilled at 118–120°/0.35 mm; yield 3.2 g. (Found C, 64.9; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.86; H, 6.7%). The ester gets readily hydrolysed with aq. NaOH at room temperature.

Cyclodehydration of Ia ($X = \text{OMe}$): 7-Methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIa, $X = \text{OMe}$) and 5-methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (IIc, $Y = \text{OMe}$): A mixture of the ester Ia ($X = \text{OMe}$) (3 g.) and sulphuric acid (27 ml.; 90%) was kept aside at room temperature (28–31°) for 65 hr. The solid product obtained after pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice, was triturated with aq. NaHCO_3 to remove 3-methoxybenzoic acid (0.2 g), formed by the hydrolysis of the ester (m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen 106–07°), filtered, washed well with water and dried; crude yield 2.3 g. On crystallisation from methanol 7-methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin crystallised as needles m.p. 130–33°. Recrystallisation gave m.p. 135–36° (Sharp); yield 1.5 g. (Found C, 70.4; H, 5.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.5; H, 5.8%) u.v. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 230, 270, 350 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.45, 4.08 and 3.62).

The mother liquor obtained after first crystallisation of the crude product gave on concentration another crop of the same isocoumarin IIa ($X = \text{OMe}$) (m.p. 128–31°). It was removed and the solution was concentrated to a small volume, and was left aside for slow crystallisation for two days when mixed crystals (needles and prisms) separated. Prism crystals were hand picked and crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°) when 5-methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin crystallised as needles, m.p. 99–100° (Found C, 70.6; H, 6.1. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.9) u.v. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} 237, 261, 346 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.24, 4.17 and 3.75).

In another method the mixture of 7-methoxy and 5-methoxy isomers obtained after removing the mother liquor was heated with aq. NaOH, filtered and acidified. The mixture of the corresponding ketones IIIa ($X = \text{OMe}$) and IIIc ($Y = \text{OMe}$) was obtained. They were separated by crystallisation from benzene (charcoal) when the ketone IIIc ($Y = \text{OMe}$)

separated as cubic crystals. They were collected and cyclodehydrated in presence of sulphuric acid (see below) when the 5-methoxy isomer (*IIc*, $Y=OMe$) was obtained. It crystallised from petrol (60-80°) as needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 99-100°; yield 0.09 g.

(±) α -Methyl- α -(2-carboxy-4-methoxyphenyl) acetone (*IIIa*, $X=OMe$): The isocoumarin *IIa* ($X=OMe$) (0.5 g.) was heated with aq. NaOH (5 ml.; 10%) on boiling water-bath till a clear solution was obtained. The solution on acidification gave a pasty solid which solidified after scratching and cooling. It crystallised from benzene-petrol (40-60°) mixture as prisms m.p. 124-126° (Found C, 65.0; H, 6.2. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.85; H, 6.35 %).

The ketone *IIIa* ($X=OMe$) (0.4 g.) on keeping mixed with sulphuric acid (4ml., 90%) at room temperature for 24hr. and then pouring on crushed ice furnished 7-methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin. It crystallised from methanol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 135-36°.

(±) α -Methyl- α -(2-carboxy-6-methoxyphenyl) acetone (*IIIc*; $Y=OMe$): The isocoumarin *IIc* ($Y=OMe$) (0.3 g.) was heated with aq. NaOH (5 ml.; 10%) on boiling water-bath, till the solution was clear. The product obtained after acidification crystallised from benzene as cubes, m.p. 158-59°; yield 0.23 g. (Found C, 65.2; H, 6.5. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.85 and H 6.35%).

The ketone *IIIc* ($Y=OMe$) (0.2 g.) cyclodehydrated on keeping with sulphuric acid (5 ml.; 90%) at room temperature for 24 hr. The product obtained after pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice, crystallised from petrol (60-80°) as needles. M.P. and mixed m.p. with the authentic 5-methoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin 99-100°; yield 0.12 g.

7-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (*IIa*; $X=OH$): The methoxyisocoumarin *IIa* ($X=OMe$) (1 g) was demethylated by heating with hydriodic acid (7 ml.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) at 130-40° in an oil bath for 3 hr. and then poured over crushed ice to which a little $NaHSO_3$ was added to remove free iodine. The solid product was well washed with aq. $NaHSO_3$ and was crystallised from ethyl acetate as prisms, m.p. 209-10°; yield 0.64 g. (Found C, 69.5; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.4 and H, 5.2%).

7-Acetoxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin was prepared by refluxing the above isocoumarin (0.3 g.) with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and pyridine (2-3 drops) for 3 hr. and then pouring on crushed ice acidified with few c.c. of conc. HCl. It crystallised from ethanol as prisms, m.p. 167-68°; yield 0.28 g. (Found C, 67.3; H, 5.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23 and H, 5.2%).

5-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylisocoumarin (*IIc*; $Y=OH$): The methoxyisocoumarin *IIc* ($Y=OMe$) (0.5 g.) was demethylated by heating with hydriodic acid (5 ml.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) at 130-40° in an oil bath and was worked up as in case of *IIa* ($X=OH$). The crude yield, 0.4 g. The product crystallised from benzene as needles, m.p. 219-20°; yield 0.35 g. (Found C, 69.8; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.47 and H, 5.2 %).

7-Methoxy-3,4-dimethylisoquinolone (*Va*; $X=OMe$): The methoxyisocoumarin *IIa* ($X=OMe$) (0.5 g.) and liquor ammonia (20 ml. of 0.88 d) was heated with reflux condenser on boiling water bath for 4 hr. During heating additional quantity of liquor ammonia (20 ml.) was added. It was then left overnight at room temperature after adding some more

of liquor ammonia (10 ml) The solution was then filtered from suspended impurities and was evaporated to dryness on water bath. The residue was washed with water and was crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as needles, m.p. 229-31° yield 0.230 g. (Found C, 70.9; H, 6.1 and N, 6.6; $C_{12}H_{13}O_2$ N requires C, 71.2; H, 5.9 and N, 6.9%).

Oxidation of α -methyl- α -(2-carboxy-4-methoxyphenyl) acetone (IIIa; X=OMe) with alkaline potassium permanganate: The ketone IIIa (X=OMe) (1 g.), aq. Na_2CO_3 (70 ml; 1%) and $KMnO_4$ (3 g.) were mixed together and refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was filtered to remove the precipitated MnO_2 . The precipitate was washed two/three times with boiling water and the filtrate and the washings were collected and concentrated to a small bulk (20 ml.). A sticky substance that was obtained after acidification was taken in ether. After removing ether it was subjected to steam distillation when a negligible amount of an oily substance went with steam (this substance was not investigated further). The solution in the flask was filtered hot to remove suspended material, then cooled saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. The semi solid obtained after removing ether, on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-petrol (40-60°) mixture furnished 4-methoxyphthalic acid as needles, m.p. 168-70° (Lit⁷. m.p. 169-70°). On sublimation it gave an anhydride, m.p. 96-97° (Lit⁷. m.p. 96-97°). On removing the solvent from the mother liquor an oily substance remained behind which was further oxidised by adding sodium hypobromite solution (4 ml. of the solution prepared by dissolving 1.6 ml. of liquid bromine in 20 ml. of 20% ice cold aq. NaOH) at room temperature. The solution was shaken and was kept aside for sometime. The heavy bromoform layer that separated was taken in ether and aq. solution was acidified when 4-methoxyphthalic acid separated in crystalline form after scratching the walls of the container. It crystallised from water as needles. M. P. and mixed m.p. with the previous sample 168-69°.

($\pm$) 4-Methoxy- α -methylhomophthalic acid (IVa; X=OMe): Sodium hypobromite solution (4 ml. of the solution prepared by adding 1.6 ml. of liquid bromine to 20 ml. of ice cold 20% aq. NaOH) was added to previously chilled solution of the ketone IIIa (X=OMe) (0.5 g.) in aq. NaOH (2 ml, 10%) and the mixture was shaken mechanically at room temperature (28-31°) for about 3 hr. The heavy bromoform layer was taken in ether and aq. solution was acidified with conc. HCl and extracted with ether. The extract was washed repeatedly with aq. $NaHSO_3$ and then with water. The substance obtained after removing ether crystallised from ethyl acetate-petrol (40-60°) mixture as needles, m.p. 145-46° (decomp.). (Found C, 58.8; H, 5.6. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.93; H, 5.4%. Eq. wt. Found 112; required 112).

($\pm$) α -Methylacetyl 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoate (Ib; X=OMe): A mixture of 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acid⁶ (6.6 g.), 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone⁵ (6 g.), K_2CO_3 (3.2 g.), methanol (60 ml.) and water (6 ml) was refluxed for 17 hr. and worked up as in case of Ia (X=OMe). The oily liquid distilled at 144-47°/0.7 mm; yield 6.5 g. (Found C, 65.8; H, 6.7. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 66.1 and H, 6.78). It is readily hydrolysed by aq. NaOH.

Cyclodehydration of Ib (X=OMe): 7-Methoxy-3, 4, 6-trimethylisocoumarin (IIb; X=OMe): The ester Ib(X=OMe) (3 g.) mixed with sulphuric acid (27 ml., 90%) was kept

6. A. N. Meldrum and W. H. Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (T) 1908, **93**, 1419.

7. W. H. Bentley and C. Weizmann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 100.

at room temperature for 48 hr. and then poured over crushed ice. The solid product was triturated with aq. NaHCO_3 to remove 3-methoxy-4-methyl-benzoic acid (formed by the hydrolysis of the ester), washed well with water and dried in vacuum (yield 1.4 g). It crystallised from dilute ethanol as needles, m.p. 124-25°; yield 0.7 g. (Found C, 71.8; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.5 and H, 6.4%). U. V. absorption in MeOH λ_{max} , 238, 272, 345 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.54, 3.95, 3.63). Concentration of the mother liquor gave a second crop of the same isocoumarin. It was removed. After removing the solvent from the mother liquor an oily residue was left behind. Attempt was made to get the other isomer (II_d; Y=OMe) from it. After crystallisation from petrol it gave a crystalline substance but with range in m.p. 105-123°. Further separation could not be undertaken as the quantity was too small.

(±) α -Methyl- α -(2-carboxy-4-methoxy-5 methyl-phenyl) acetone (III_b; X=OMe) was prepared as in case of III_a (X=OMe) by heating the isocoumarin II_b (X=OMe) (1 g.) with aq. NaOH on boiling water bath for 2 hr. and then acidifying the solution. It crystallised from benzene-petrol (40-60°) mixture as needles, m.p. 104-06°; yield 0.78 g. (Found C, 66.4, H, 6.4. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 6.7%).

This acetone derivative (0.5 g) cyclodehydrated readily on heating with sulphuric acid (10 ml., 90%) for 17 hr. at room temperature. The product obtained after pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice, crystallised from dil. ethanol as needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic 7-methoxy-3,4,6-trimethylisocoumarin 124-25°; yield 0.25 g.

7-Methoxy-3,4,6-trimethylisoquinolone (V_b; X=OMe): It was prepared by following the same procedure as in case of the isoquinolone (V_a, X=OMe) by the action of liquor ammonia (in all 40 ml.) on the methoxy isocoumarin II_b (X=OMe) (0.5 g.) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml.). It crystallised from ethylacetate-petrol (40-60°) mixture as needles, m.p. 262-63°; yield 0.21g. (Found C, 71.8; H, 6.8 and N, 6.45. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 71.8; H, 6.9 and N, 6.4%).

7-Hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethylisocoumarin (II_b, X=OH): The methoxyisocoumarin (II_b, X=OMe) (0.5 g.) was demethylated by refluxing with hydrotic acid (7 ml.) and acetic anhydride (1 ml.) and the reaction mixture was worked up as in case of demethylation of II_a (X=OMe). The product crystallised from dilute ethanol as needles, m.p. 269-70°; yield 0.36 g. (Found C, 70.6; H, 6.0. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.5 and H, 5.9%).

Acetyl derivative of this isocoumarin was prepared as usual by heating the isocoumarin (0.2 g.) with acetic anhydride (4 ml.) and pyridine (few drops). It crystallised from ethanol as needles m.p. 158-59°; yield 0.2 g. (Found C, 68.4; H, 5.7. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.7%).

(±) 4-Methoxy- α , 5-dimethylhomophthalic acid (IV_b; X=OMe): It was prepared in the same manner as in case of IV_a (X=OMe) by oxidising the ketone III_b (X=OMe) (0.5 g.) in aq. NaOH (2 ml., 10%) with sodium hypobromite solution* (4.5 ml.). It crystallised from ethyl acetate-petrol (40-60°) mixture as cubes, m.p. 177-78° (decomp.); yield 0.280 g. (Found C, 60.2; H, 5.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.5 and H, 5.9%).

*The solution was prepared as in case of (IV_a; X=OMe)

α -*Methylacetyl-3-hydroxybenzoate* (Ia; X=OH) was prepared as in case of Ia (X=OMe) by refluxing *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid (5.6 g.), 1-bromoethyl methyl ketone⁵ (6 g.), K₂CO₃ (3.2 g.), methanol (60 ml.) and water (6 ml.) for 17 hr. and worked up as usual. The oily substance that was obtained initially solidified on cooling. It crystallised from benzene-petrol (40-60°) as needles, m p. 72-74°; yield 5.0 g. (Found C, 63.2; H, 5.9. C₁₁H₁₂O₄ requires C, 63.46 and H, 5.7%).

Cyclodehydration of Ia (X=OH): 7-Hydroxy-3, 4-dimethyl-isocoumarin (IIa, X=OH):

The ester (Ia, X=OH) (2 g.) was well mixed with sulphuric acid (18 ml., 90%) and was kept aside for 48 hr. at room temperature and then poured on crushed ice. The solid product was triturated with aq NaHCO₃ and then washed thoroughly with water and dried; yield 0.8 g. It crystallised from ethylacetate-petrol (40-60°) mixture (charcoal) to give m.p. 188-200°. This was allowed to recrystallise from excess of ethyl acetate when initially some compound separated, m.p. 190-95°. It was filtered and the mother liquor was concentrated when 7-hydroxy-3, 4-dimethyl-isocoumarin crystallised as needles, m.p. 206-209°. Recrystallisation of the same from ethyl acetate gave m p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen (obtained by demethylation of 7-methoxy-3, 4-dimethyl isocoumarin) 209-10°. Attempt was made to obtain the 5-hydroxyisocoumarin (11c, Y=OH) in pure state from crop of the crystals with m p. 190-195° but it was not successful.

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